

Effect of NaCl Salinity in Genotypic Variation of Maize (*Zea mays* L.) During Early Growth Stage in Low Land soil of Ethiopia

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ABSTRACT:

Salt stress is the main problem during crop production at the agricultural land. This study was conducted to screen the maize genotypes for salt tolerance under salt stress condition using agronomical traits. The pot experimental treatments were used four NaCl salinity levels (0, 80, 160 and 240 mM) and nine maize genotypes (61006, Mal-1, Mal.hybrid, 215065, MHQ, 207346, 227235, M-130 and 61036). It was arranged in factorial Complete Randomize Design with three replicates. Data was analyzed using SAS, SPSS and Minitab-6 statistical software and means were separated by least significance difference (LSD). Eight agronomic traits (shoot length, root length, shoot fresh weight, root fresh weight, shoot dry weight, root dry weight, seedling root reduction and seedling shoot reduction) were measured. The ANOVA for treatments of genotypes and their interaction was found to be highly significant ($p < 0.05$) with regard to root fresh weight (RFW), shoot fresh weight (SHFW), root dry weight (RDW), shoot dry weight (SHDW) and seedling root reduction (SRR). Genotypes MHQ, 207346 and Mal.hybrid were found in a highly salt tolerant during seedling growth stage. However, genotypes 227235 and 61006 were salt sensitive, and the rest genotypes were intermediate in their salt tolerance. The correlation analysis showed a highly positive significant correlation between shoot length (SHL) and shoot fresh weight (SHFW). Cluster analysis was carried out to set genotypes into different groups. The agronomical traits method was an effective, easy and affordable technique for assessment of salt-tolerant genotypes which will be useful for plant breeders.

Keyword: Maize, NaCl, alinity, Seedling traits

INTRODUCTION

Soil salinity is one of the major environmental abiotic stresses that limit agricultural productivity and food supply of worldwide. It is a serious problem of limiting agricultural productivity in many regions of the world [25]. Nearly 10% of the earth's land is salt affected and an estimated 10 million hectare of agricultural land is lost annually due to salinization and water logging [4]. But also in Ethiopia, salt-affected soils are prevalent in the Rift Valley and the lowland areas. For instance, Awash Valley is one of lower plains, particularly dominated by salt-affected soils [28].

However, the existing soil salinity problems in crop production will become worse due to rapidly growing human population in many countries and the increasing of over limited water resources which are forcing growers to use poor quality water for irrigation. In saline soil, water inhibits plant growth by an osmotic effect, which reduces the ability of plant to take up water and by ion excess, which affects the plant cells [13]. Seed germination and seedling growth represent major problem to establish a vigorous crop stand. Therefore, these growths stage can be utilized to screen plant germplasm for salt tolerance [7]. Though, maize (*Zea mays* L.) is the third most important cereal in the world after wheat and rice, and grows under a wide range of climatic conditions. It is the most salt-sensitive cereal crop [6]. Most of crop plants are sensitive to salt solution at 0-80 mM, moderately tolerant 160-230 mM and more tolerant above 240 mM [12]. Salt resistance is an inherent trait of plants to withstand the adverse effects in the leaves and root zone [24]. There are also various detrimental effects of salt stress in crop plants, responsible for severe decreases in the crop plant growth and yield of plants, depending on the plant species, salinity levels, and ionic composition of the salts [29].

Screening of maize germplasm is important to determine genetic potential for salt tolerance which strengthens the breeders for producing high yielding and salt tolerant maize genotypes. The variation among the genotypes for the physiological indices at germination and early seedling stages has been analyzed in many crop plants [14]. However, the availability of genetic variation both at intra or inter-specific level is a prerequisite for the success of breeding programs. Genetic variability for salt tolerance was reported in alfalfa [18], *Trifolium* [5], sunflower [8], rice [11], safflower [21] and maize [22]. Therefore, this study attempted to investigate the genetic variability of maize (*Zea mays* L.) genotypes which can grow in the lowland areas of Ethiopia for salt stress during seedling growth stage.

2. METHODOLOGY

Nine maize (*Zea mays* L.) genotypes were used in this experiment (61006, Mal-1, Mal.hybrid, 215065, MHQ, 207346, 227235, M-130 and 61036). These genotypes were obtained from Melkassa Agricultural Research Center and Institute of Biodiversity Conservation (IBC). In the study area, most of the farmers are used these genotypes. Genotypes are good for their morphological traits (height 1.90 cm, root length 16-25 cm, stem thickness 4-6 cm in diameter, leaf kernel number 2-4), they produce quite yield at arid and semi-arid areas.

The experiment was conducted by modified procedures used by Ahmed [1] using plastic pots with width 15 cm at the base and 20 cm at the top and 18 cm height. Nine maize genotypes were treated with four different concentrations of salinity levels NaCl 0, 80, 160 and 240 mM, respectively. Distilled water (0 mM) was used

as a control. After the salt concentration was adjusted, 1.5 kg of agricultural soil which is fertile, deep, well drained clay loam to silty loam soils with good water holding capacity was weighed and filled into 108 pots. Then, nine surface sterilized uniform seeds of each maize genotype were sown in the pots at uniform depth. Pots were arranged in a factorial based on a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) placement and was replicated 3 times. The seedling growth parameters were obtained after 21st days. Data was collected at the 21st day from the length of shoots and roots of three seedlings from each pot were measured using a draftsman ruler. Also, it was collected from shoot fresh weight, root fresh weight, root dry weight and shoot dry weight of three seedlings were measured and expressed in gram as fresh condition for the first two parameters and expressed in gram after oven drying at 70 °C until a constant weight was reached for the second two parameters and was measured on digital analytical balance [17]. Seedling root reduction (SRR) and shoot reduction (SHR) were calculated according to the following formula [14], respectively.

$$\text{SRR (\%)} = \frac{\text{Root length of control} - \text{Root length of treatment}}{\text{Root length of treatment}} \times 100$$

$$\text{SHR\%} = \frac{\text{Plant Height at control} - \text{Plant height at Saline condition}}{\text{Plant height at Saline condition}} \times 100$$

Table 1. Analysis of variance on Mean Squares of measured traits of maize genotypes under salinity stress

Source of variance	DF	RFW	SHFW	RDW	SHDW	SRR
SL	3	0.235**	6.230**	0.011**	0.167**	1007.362**
Genotype	8	0.042**	0.168**	0.008**	0.018**	87.342**
SL x varieties	24	0.009**	0.840**	0.003*	0.005*	52.944*
Error	35	0.00	0.250	0.00	0.001	24.621

*, **Significant at 5% and 1% probability levels

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for maize agronomic traits

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Shoot height length	36	21.6	53.66	43.32	7.81
Root length	36	24.28	50.69	33.75	7.05
Root fresh weight	36	0.22	1.06	0.48	0.18
Shoot fresh weight	36	1.08	4.69	2.70	0.79
Root dry weight	36	0.07	0.52	0.17	0.07
Shoot dry weight	36	0.27	0.87	0.58	0.14
Seedling root reduction	36	0.00	44.07	9.77	9.37
Seedling shoot reduction	36	0.00	57.20	14.35	13.71

Effect of Salt Stress on Maize Agronomic Traits

The experiment was carried out to observe the influence of salinity on the seedling growth of maize genotypes. The results obtained indicated that the increment of salt concentration can cause delayed emergence of plumule and radicle as compared to control. At the early seedling stage, reduction in root length and shoot length clearly demonstrated genetic variation in vegetative growth responses to salinity among maize genotypes.

Root fresh weight

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed a significant variation among genotypes ($p \leq 0.05$) for average root fresh weight (RFW). Genotype*treatment interaction effect was also significant reflecting all the accessions and varieties responding differently to salt stress with respect to average root fresh weight (RFW). Increased salinity levels resulted in a decreased average root fresh weight (RFW) in accessions 61006, 215065 and 61036 and variety Mal-1. Nevertheless, average root fresh weight (RFW), brought about no more influence in variety MHQ by salt

Plant height at saline condition

STUDY AREA

The experiment was conducted in the greenhouse at Bule Hora University, Oromia, Ethiopia from.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The data were analyzed using ANOVA and subsequent comparison of means was performed using the Duncan's Test at 5% probability level. The cluster analysis and coefficient of variation analysis were performed by using the SAS for manipulating data and recoding data, SPSS summarizing data in the form of tables and graphs and Minitab-6 describing the relationship among agronomic traits.

Analysis of variance showed that there were significant differences between salinity levels. The results of this study revealed that various concentrations of NaCl had a significant effect on the all measured traits for maize genotypes. And also, analysis of variance showed that interaction effects were significant for all investigated traits (Table 1).

In this study, descriptive statistics might help us to manage the data set and present it in the summarized form (Table 2)

stress up to 240 mM shown in (Figure1a).

Shoot fresh weight

However, the influence of salt stress became pronounced with higher salt concentrations (Figure1b). From the entire genotypes considered, accessions 61006, 2272 and 61036 were the salt affected as compared to the control. However, accessions 207346 and varieties MHQ, Mal.hybrid and M-130 medium salt-affected genotypes.

Root dry weight

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) confirmed the presence of a significant variation in average root dry weight among genotypes ($P \leq 0.05$). The root dry weight has no great change as salt concentration is increased as compared to the control (Figure1c).

Shoot dry weight

The differences between the means of genotypes (Figure1d) and salinity stress levels were compared by Duncan multiple range test. It was observed that in all genotypes, there was a decrease in shoot dry weight because increment of salinity stress in certain

genotypes caused physiological disturbance in their cell. Among the maize genotypes, varieties Mal.hybrid, M-130 and Mal-1 and accession 61036 and 227235 had the highest shoot dry weight at 80 and 160 mM as compared to control relatively. However, the maximum reduction in shoot dry weight was observed at the highest level, that is, 240 mM of NaCl salinity stress.

Seedling root reduction

There is reduction of seedling root length in 61006, 227235 and Mal-1 as it was observed at 240 mM salinity levels in comparison with the left genotypes (Figure 1e)

Figure 1(a-e). Effects of different salinity levels on Root fresh weight, Shoot fresh weight, Root dry weight, Shoot dry weight and Seedling root reduction of maize (*Zea mays* L.) Genotypes

Table 3. Correlation coefficients among studied agronomic traits of maize genotypes under different salinity stress.

	SHL	RL	RFW	SHFW	RDW	SHDW	SRR	SSHR
SHL	1	0.477**	0.600**	0.844**	0.437**	0.745**	-0.643**	-0.852**
RL		1	0.584**	0.382*	0.422*	0.373*	-0.408*	-0.333
RFW			1	0.777**	0.609**	0.668**	-0.644**	-0.611**
SHFW				1	0.517**	0.823**	-0.724**	-0.845**
RDW					1	0.470**	-0.416*	-0.334
SHDW						1	-0.628**	-0.790**
SRR							1	0.805**
SSHR								1

*, ** Significant at 0.05 and 0.01 probability levels, respectively

SHL=Shoot length, RL=Root length, RFW= Root fresh weight, SHFW= shoot fresh weight, RDW= Root dry weight, SHDW= Shoot dry weight, SRR= Seedling root reduction, SSHR= Seedling shoot reduction

Correlation Analysis

The correlation analysis showed a highly positive significant correlation between shoot length (SHL) and shoot fresh weight (SHFW), and also between shoot fresh weight (SHFW) and shoot dry weight (SHDW) (Table 3). On the other hand, shoot length (SHL) and shoot fresh weight (SHFW) was depicted a negative

cluster analysis are arranged maize genotypes into three groups. The result of the first cluster which was included one accession 61006. The results of the second cluster which was included six of the maize varieties and accessions Mal-1, MHQ, M-130, Mal.hybrid and 215065, 227235, and third cluster includes two accessions 204376 and 61036. From three clusters, cluster one, three and two were shown high sensitive, moderate and tolerant salinity stress, respectively.

4. DISCUSSION

Analysis of variance for all agronomic traits showed that the salinity levels and their interaction for root fresh weight, shoot fresh weight, root dry weight, shoot dry weight and seedling root reduction in maize genotypes was found to be significant at 5% level (Figure 1a-e) and reflecting that each genotype differently responded to salt stress with respect to all agronomic traits. It is an established fact that tolerance at adult stage is reflected by the tolerance at seedling stage of plant. However, the reduction was sharp at 160 and 240 mM NaCl salinity levels. On the basis of root fresh weight for the soils having 240mM of salinity, the genotypes MHQ, M-130 and 227235 can be recommended. Like other workers, results of our study also depicted that salinity caused a reduction in plant fresh weight as well as dry weight of maize genotypes [10]. Accession 207346 and varieties MHQ, Mal.hybrid and M-130 had medium shoot fresh weight. The results were in partly accordance with Misra and Dwivedi [19], which reported that the fresh weight and dry weight (figure 1a-d) in seedlings were decreased by salinity stress. In maize, the variation at seedling stage affects the yield potential at maturity [2]. Consequently, physiological traits would be very useful in salinity tolerance improvement programs especially, shoot fresh weight which has shown a regular growth reduction compared to the controls. The results of the present study are in agreement with the results achieved by Giaveno *et al.* [9] in screening tropical maize for salt tolerance. There is no reduction of seedling root length at 0 mM salinity levels in comparison with the other salinity levels. According to Mladenova [20] found that the tolerant genotypes of maize had the higher growth rate reduction under enhanced salt stress.

The analysis of relationship among these traits and their association with seed yield is essential to establish selection criteria for salinity stress [27]. The correlation analysis showed a highly positive significant correlation between shoot length (SHL) and shoot fresh weight (SHFW) ($= 0.844^{**}$). Shoot length (SHL) and shoot fresh weight (SHFW) were depicted a negative and significant correlation with seedling shoot reduction (SSHR) ($= -0.643^{**}$ and $= -0.852^{**}$), respectively. Strong positive correlation with grain yield which indicated selection of both these characters simultaneously for breeding programs and these results were in accordance with those of Ali *et al.* [3] for sorghum landrace. Our results in maize genotypes were in agreement with previous studies in which the concentration of Na^+ and Cl^- ions are negative correlation within physiological indices that leads salt to injure plant cells [26]. According to our results, maize genotypes at seedling stage are might be affected due to high concentration of salts in the soil solution at root zone which exceeds certain limits, and toxic effects of Na^+ and Cl^- ions to their metabolic pathway which interfere balanced absorption of essential nutritional ions by seedlings.

CONCLUSION

The results of the current study also showed increasing the amount of salt stress caused a significant reduction in seedling root length of some genotypes. Genotypes MHQ, 207346 and Mal.hybrid

produced significantly higher seedling root length than the other genotypes in the 240 mM NaCl salinity level though most of the genotypes could not produce sufficient root growth. Neumann [10] indicated that salinity can rapidly inhibit root growth and hence capacity of water uptake and essential mineral nutrition from soil. Plants vary in their tolerance to salinity that depends on their efficiency of root system with regards to nutrient absorption and K, Na uptake discrimination or mainly the translocation of sodium and chloride ions. In maize, sodium mainly remained in roots as compared to shoots that might be due to the mechanism of retention more of Na^+ in roots [16] as compared to other plant parts. This finding clearly indicated that positive and significant correlations among different indices and cluster analysis also proved that maize genotypes were screened on the basis of physiological indices are salt tolerant. Tolerant genotypes can directly be recommended for cultivation on salt affected soils or can be used to develop high yielding genotypes for ensuring sustainable production in arid and semi-arid areas.

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